

Design and Assessment of 3-DOF Nano-gimbal for Spatial Manipulation

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Abstract—High-precision spatial manipulation and measurement require high-ratio vibration reduction and high positioning accuracy devices, in the presence of multi-degree-of-freedom (MDOF) vibrations and varying direction payload. In this paper, to ensure the positioning accuracy of the end-effector, a 3-DOF nano-gimbal is designed, which integrates a proposed 3-DOF tuned mass damper (TMD) for vibration suppression and a flexure-based nanopositioner for steady-state precision. Furthermore, as the critical part of vibration suppression, the modeling and design of 3-DOF TMD are analyzed and discussed in detail, considering both passive and active cases. First, the design and modeling of a 3-DOF nano-gimbal are presented, which is modeled by the modal decomposition method to obtain a set of decoupled motion equations. Then, the TMD is parameterized and optimized, where the passive case is designed by harmonic response methods, and the control law of the active case is designed by equivalent dynamics coefficients with state estimation. Finally, the performances of TMD and active tuned mass damper (ATMD) are evaluated by a set of simulations, including frequency and time domain assessments.

Index Terms—Vibration control, compliant mechanism, tuned mass damper, nano-gimbal

I. INTRODUCTION

With the rapid advancement of high-end components, spatial manipulation, and measurement have garnered widespread attention, including large panel surface inspection with atomic force microscopy [1], parallel machine tool [2], and robotic milling [3], as illustrated in Fig.1(a). Due to the high-precision requirements of the end-effector, achieving high-performances of vibration isolation in terms of high-ratio suppression and high positioning accuracy of the aforementioned application

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Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of spatial manipulation system. (a) Spatial manipulation system. (b) Varying direction payload of end-effector. (c) 3-DOF translational vibrations and the suppression.

has been a key issue for implementation, in the presence of disturbances, coupling effect, and noise.

To address this problem, the passive and active vibration isolation approaches can be considered. The passive methods suppress vibrations by a low-stiffness system, which works above the natural frequency with a factor of $\sqrt{2}$. However, these approaches suffer from the MDOF vibrations with varying direction payload, resulting in a trade-off between kinetic decoupling to reduce parasitic motion and compactness, as illustrated in Fig.1(b). On the other hand, active methods could cancel the MDOF vibrations with well decoupling toward varying direction payload and offer high positioning accuracy, due to the high-stiffness property [4], [5]. Nevertheless, limited by the waterbed effect, the control design encounters the problem of simultaneously achieving high bandwidth to reject

Fig. 2. Conceptual design of 3-DOF nano-gimbal.

the disturbances, and high control gain at the frequencies where vibrations occur, as shown in Fig.1(c).

To this end, a 3-DOF nano-gimbal is proposed in this paper, which suppresses the vibrations by a novel 3-DOF compliant TMD to absorb the energy at the desired band, then rejects the disturbances to ensure high-precision positioning by a flexure-based nanopositioner. Thanks to the advantages of compactness and symmetrical kinematics [6], [7], the flexure-based compliant mechanism technology is adopted to achieve a 3-DOF TMD that deals with the problem of MDOF vibrations with varying direction payload. The parameterization and optimization of TMD are presented in cases of passive and active. Finally, a set of simulations is conducted and proves the effectiveness and difference between TMD and ATMD.

II. DESIGN AND MODELING OF 3-DOF NANO-GIMBAL

In this section, the main purpose is to illustrate design and modeling of the proposed 3-DOF nano-gimbal.

A. System design

The system is designed to be connected between the end-effector and moving part of the original device, which consists of a base to combine the components for self-stabilization, a TMD, and a XYZ nanopositioner, as shown in Fig.2. The compliant 3-DOF TMD is designed with the mass blocks placed at the center, and then moved by the connecting flexure beams. Due to the symmetrical parallel structure of the compliant mechanism, the movement of TMD is decoupled ideally. The 3-DOF nanopositioner is to ensure the positioning of the end-effector, thus high stiffness for sufficient bandwidth and accuracy should be obtained.

B. Compliance modeling of 3-DOF TMD

Here, the compliance model of TMD is established to present the relationship between mechanical property and the designed dimensional parameters of flexure components, as shown in Fig.3. The flexure components in TMD are represented by springs in the figure. First, the X-axis and Y-axis decoupled mechanisms are utilized to enable the related motion of mass block, where the motion of single-DOF is transferred by two pairs of parallelogram structures, namely

Fig. 3. Compliance modeling of TMD.

Fig. 4. Dynamics model (a) Main structure with 3-DOF TMD. (b) Single-DOF dynamics model.

decoupling and guiding mechanism, respectively. Since orthogonal to horizontal motion, the z-axis is only needed a set of guiding mechanisms. To determine the stiffness of one parallelogram structure, it can be calculated by:

$$C_p = K_p^{-1} = \left(\sum_{i=1}^4 K_{b,i}^{-1} \right)^{-1} \quad (1)$$

where C_p is the compliance, K_p is the stiffness of mechanism, and $K_{b,i}$ is the stiffness of the flexure beam. Then, the stiffness of one beam can be derived by follows:

$$K_{b,i} = \frac{F}{d} = \frac{Eb_i h_i^3}{l_i^3} \quad (2)$$

where E is the Young's modulus. b_i , h_i , and l_i are the width, thickness, and length of the flexure beam, respectively. By (1) and (2), the TMD can be designed to obtain the desired stiffness, that works for vibration absorption.

C. Dynamics modeling of system

Generally, to express the behavior of a mechanical system excited by an external force, the modal decomposition theory is utilized to split the total vibration pattern into separate resonating sub-patterns, that is eigenmodes. By this method, the movement of the proposed system can be written as:

$$M_i \ddot{q}(t) + C_i \dot{q}(t) + K_i q(t) = \phi_i^T F(t) \quad (3)$$

where ω_f and ξ_f are the resonant frequency and damping ratio of $N(s)$, respectively. By (13) and (14), x_1 and x_2 are estimated.

Additionally, in the active case, the high stiffness of ATMD is designed to prove high dynamics performance controls for vibration absorption. Thus, let k_{2a} and c_{2a} denote the stiffness and damping coefficient of ATMD. Then, (4) is rewritten as:

$$m_2\ddot{x}_2 = u_2 - c_{2a}(\dot{x}_2 - \dot{x}_1) - k_{2a}(x_2 - x_1) \quad (16)$$

Here, the control law of ATMD is designed as:

$$u_2 = k_a(x_2 - x_1) + c_a(\dot{x}_2 - \dot{x}_1) - m_1gs^2x_1 \quad (17)$$

where k_a and c_a are the design parameters to actively tune the dynamics factors of ATMD. The gain g is to provide a inertia force to further suppress the peaks of the TMD response function. The control objective of u_2 is to offer a motion that is equivalent to the TMD. Combining (16) and (17) yield:

$$\begin{aligned} m_2\ddot{x}_2 &= u_2 - c_{2a}(\dot{x}_2 - \dot{x}_1) - k_{2a}(x_2 - x_1) \\ &= -(c_a + c_{2a})(\dot{x}_2 - \dot{x}_1) - (k_a + k_{2a})(x_2 - x_1) \\ &\quad - m_1gs^2x_1 \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Then, comparing (4) and (18), we get:

$$k_a = k_2 - k_{2a}, c_a = c_2 - c_{2a} \quad (19)$$

In terms of stability, by (13), it is obtained that x_2 can be stabilized when x_1 is internally stable. Therefore, the transfer function from u_2 to x_1 is derived as:

$$\frac{X_1(s)}{U_2(s)} = \frac{m_2s^2 + (c_2 - c_a)s + (k_2 - k_a)}{As^4 + B_2s^3 + Cs^2 + Ds + E} \quad (20)$$

where

$$\begin{cases} A = -m_1m_2g \\ B = -m_1gc_2 \\ C = c_a c_2 - m_2 - m_1gk_2 \\ D = c_2k_a + c_a k_2 + c_2 \\ E = k_2k_a + k_2 \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

By (20), to ensure stability, the following conditions should be guaranteed:

$$c_2 \geq c_a, k_2 \geq k_a, g < 1 \quad (22)$$

Recalling the control law (19), we get (22) always holds when g is kept within $[0,1]$, thus it is closed-loop stable.

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

To validate the effectiveness and difference of TMD and ATMD, a series of simulations are conducted. The coefficients of the system are listed in Table.I, where the main structure is with a large mass. The natural frequency of TMD is set to be matched with the base, thus an ideal vibration suppression is obtained. Furthermore, the mass ratio of both TMD and ATMD is 5 %, according to (10). For ATMD, to provide a

TABLE I
COEFFICIENTS OF THE SYSTEM.

Unit	m (kg)	k (N/m)	c (N-s/m)	Natural frequency (Hz)
Base	10	1×10^6	63.25	50.33
TMD	0.5	5×10^4	37.95	50.33
ATMD	0.5	5×10^6	3.80	503.29
Nanopositioner	1	5×10^7	2.83	1125.39

Fig. 6. FEA results of TMD. (a) The analyzed model. (b) The FEA frequency response results.

Fig. 7. Frequency response results. (a) From u_1 to x_1 . (b) From u_1 to x_3 .

Fig. 8. The built simulation of comparisons.

high-dynamics motion, the stiffness k_2 is increased by 2 orders of magnitude. Similarly, a nanopositioner is designed with a high bandwidth to offer high-precision positioning.

A. Frequency domain

First, the effectiveness of TMD is demonstrated by FEA in Ansys/Workbench. The model is built as Fig.6(a), where the

Fig. 9. Comparison results. (a) x_3 . (b) x_2 .

Fig. 10. Triangular trajectory tracking results.

main structure is represented as a compliant mechanism that with the same resonant frequency as the base. From Fig.6(b), it can be seen that the magnitude at resonant frequency of main structure is suppressed over 90 % by TMD.

Here, the frequency response of TMD and ATMD are displayed in Fig.7, generated by Matlab/Simulink as shown in Fig.8. From Fig.7(a), it can be observed that the resonant peak of x_1 in 50 Hz is damped by TMD, but produces two resonant peaks behind it. The peak is perfect damped by ATMD, while the open-loop gain in low-frequency is increased a little. By the above analysis, we see ATMD could provide a better vibration suppression than TMD in this case. Additionally, the coupling from x_3 leads to an anti-resonance and resonance beyond 1000 Hz with a magnitude lower than -40 dB, indicating that this effect can be neglected in TMD design.

For nanopositioner, the damping results of TMD and ATMD are the same as x_1 , as shown in Fig.7(b). Different from x_1 , only one resonant peak is located at about 1000 Hz with a magnitude of -30 dB. Due to the high-stiffness of nanopositioner, m_1 and m_3 can be viewed as rigidly connection in low frequency. Therefore, the dynamics of x_1 and x_3 are almost the same in low frequency, implying that the effort of TMD on base does work simultaneously on nanopositioner.

B. Time domain

To further study the difference between TMD and ATMD, they are tested and analyzed in the time domain. To simulate disturbance in the places where may exist, u_1 and u_3 are two

Fig. 11. Actuator saturation results.

step signals with different amplitudes in two moments, which are represented as:

$$u_1 = 20\varepsilon(t - 0.1), u_3 = 0.5\varepsilon(t - 0.3) \quad (23)$$

Here, the step response results are plotted in Fig.9. It can be seen that the result of ATMD of x_3 is stabilized much faster than TMD, which larger overshoot. After the overshoot, x_3 of ATMD is stable, while the case of TMD experiences residual vibration for a long time. For x_2 , we see ATMD offers a fast response when disturbance inputs than TMD, and keeps stationary fast. Recalling (16), it can be obtained that ATMD has higher stiffness than TMD, thus fast response can be provided, that is the reason why the system is damped better by ATMD. Limited by the inherent dynamics of TMD, the phase lag of -90° at the resonant frequency is unavoidable, thus TMD may not be adapted to the high-speed application. To confirm the above conclusion, the triangular trajectory with 1 Hz is adopted as the desired signal, whose results also verify the effectiveness of ATMD under high-speed case as shown in Fig.10.

In the case of ATMD, the constraints of the actuator must be considered, where the biggest problem is the actuator saturation, the so-called wind-up effect. To study this issue, the simulations are set the same as (23), and various constraints of u_2 are set, as shown in Fig.11. From the results, it is noted that reducing the allowable output force of u_2 leads to a decrease in overshoot and results in residual vibrations persisting for a longer duration. In the case of < 5 N, the result of ATMD is worse than TMD.

In summary, ATMD offers a better performance than TMD, but the control constraints must be considered. Fortunately, in high-precision applications, the slight vibrations can be addressed by using a piezo-actuator, which can provide a force that with more than hundreds or even thousands of Newton easily.

C. A control design example of nanopositioner

To demonstrate the effect of TMD on the control design of nanopositioner, a controller for u_3 is designed with the same control strategy and objective. Due to the flexible connection of TMD, the positioning accuracy is limited by the low open-loop gain of the plant at a low-frequency range [9]. To this end,

Fig. 12. Control design results.

Fig. 13. Pole-zero mapping from u_3 to x_3 .

an integrator is utilized as the tracking controller to regular the control signal of two cases. The design objective is to ensure a phase margin of about 45° , and then to observe the achieved bandwidth. According to the above situations, the controller parameters are tuned as shown in Fig.12. It can be seen that the bandwidth of TMD is achieved as 3 Hz, while ATMD is up to 27 Hz. Both two methods show good damping on the resonant peak, while ATMD offers better performances but it encounters more considerations in terms of control constraints. With passive damping at resonance, a sharp change in gain results in significant phase rolling off within that range, severely limiting the bandwidth of TMD.

Moreover, the bandwidth in tuning results is too low, limited by the resonant peak of x_1 and phase lag of the integrator. In practice, this problem could be addressed by utilizing other tracking control strategies, or active damping methods, such as notch filter [10] and positive position feedback.

From the viewpoint of vibration modes, pole-zero mapping is used to further identify the difference between TMD and ATMD. The results displayed in Fig.13 indicate that the modes of x_1 and x_2 are more effectively damped by ATMD compared to TMD. This is proved by relocating the poles and zeros to

left side or closer to the real axis by ATMD in the pole-zero mapping. Besides, the poles of resonant mode of x_3 at 1100 Hz are almost unchanged, because these high-frequency poles are outside the bandwidth.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a 3-DOF nano-gimbal is proposed for precision enhancement of spatial manipulation and measurement, by means of MDOF vibrations absorption and rejection. From the viewpoint of development, the parameterization and optimization of passive TMD and ATMD are presented, where a state estimator of ATMD is designed and the stability of control law is analyzed. To validate the effectiveness of TMD and ATMD, a set of simulations are performed, which demonstrate the performances and differences between the two cases.

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